

Iterative Process for a Common Fixed Point of a Finite Family of Asymptotically k -Pseudocontractive Maps

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Abstract:

Let K be a closed convex nonempty subset of a Hilbert space H and let $\{T_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a finite family of Asymptotically k -pseudocontractive maps from K into itself with $F = \bigcap_{i=1}^N F(T_i)$ not empty. Sufficient conditions for the strong convergence of the sequence of successive approximations generated by a Picard-like process to a common fixed point of the family are proved.

Keywords: Hilbert space, Asymptotically k -pseudocontractive, compact, boundedly compact, semi-compact, demi-compact, common fixed point, finite family, Picard process.

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Introduction

Let K be nonempty subset of a Hilbert space H . K is said to be (sequentially) compact if every bounded sequence in K has a subsequence that converges in K and is said to be boundedly compact if every bounded subset of K is compact. In finite dimensional spaces, closed subsets are boundedly compact.

Given a subset S of K , we shall denote by $\text{co}(S)$ and $\text{ccl}(S)$ the *convex hull* and the *closed convex hull* of S respectively. If K is boundedly compact convex and S is bounded, $\text{co}(S)$ and hence $\text{ccl}(S)$ are compact convex subsets of K .

Let E be a normed linear space. A map $T: K \rightarrow E$ is said to be *semi-compact* if for any bounded sequence $\{x_n\} \subset K$ such that

$\|x_n - Tx_n\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ there exists a subsequence $\{x_{n_j}\} \subset \{x_n\}$ such that $\{x_{n_j}\}$ converges strongly to some x^* in K .

The map T is said to be *demi-compact* at z in E if for any bounded sequence $\{x_n\} \subset K$ such that

$\|x_n - Tx_n\| \rightarrow z$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ there exist a subsequence $\{x_{n_j}\} \subset \{x_n\}$

and a point p in K such that $\{x_{n_j}\}$ converges strongly to p (Observe that if T is additionally continuous, then $p - Tp = z$).

A nonlinear map $T: K \rightarrow E$ is said to be *completely continuous* if it maps bounded sets into

relatively compact sets, and is said to be *Lipschitzian* if $\exists \lambda$

$L \geq 0$ such that

$$\|Tx - Ty\| \leq L \|x - y\| \quad \text{for all } x, y \text{ in } K$$

If $L = 1$ then T is called *nonexpansive* and if $L < 1$ then the mapping T is called a *contraction*. A self-map T on K is said to be *uniformly L-Lipschitzian* if there exists $L \geq 0$ such that

$$\|T^n x - T^n y\| \leq L \|x - y\| \quad \text{for all } x, y \text{ in } K, \text{ for all } n \text{ in } \mathbb{N} \text{ (set of natural numbers).}$$

The mapping T with domain $D(T)$ and the range $R(T)$ in H is called pseudocontractive if for all x, y in $D(T)$,

$$\|Tx - Ty\|^2 \leq \|x - y\|^2 + \|(I-T)x - (I-T)y\|^2 \quad (2)$$

If (eq:2) holds for all x in $D(T)$ and y in $F(T)$ (the fixed point set of T),

then T is said to be hemiccontractive. T is k -pseudocontractive or strictly pseudocontractive in the sense of Browder-Petryshyn [1] if there exists k in $(0,1)$ such that for all x, y in $D(T)$,

$$\|Tx - Ty\|^2 \leq \|x - y\|^2 + k \|(I-T)x - (I-T)y\|^2 \quad (3)$$

T is asymptotically k -pseudocontractive if there exists $\{a_n\}$ in $[1, \infty)$ and k in $(0,1)$ such that $a_n \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and

$$\|T^n x - T^n y\|^2 \leq a_n \|x - y\|^2 + k \|(I-T^n)x - (I-T^n)y\|^2 \quad \text{for all } x, y \text{ in } K; \text{ for all } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

The class of k -pseudocontractive maps and their likes have been studied by various authors (Browder & Petryshyn, 1967; Chidume & Moore, 1999; Chidume, 1984; Hicks & Kubicek, 1977; Moore & Nnoli, 2001; Moore, Nnubia, & Akabuike, 2015; Moore, Nnubia, & Nfor, 2010; Osilike, 1993; Weng, 1993; Wong, 1974).

Browder and Petryshyn (1967) introduced the map and proved that the Mann iteration converges strongly to a fixed point of such map

defined on a compact convex subset of a Hilbert space.

Our purpose in this paper is to extend the result of Browder-Petryshyn (1976) to the case of a finite family of asymptotically k -pseudocontractive self-maps of a closed convex nonempty subset of a Hilbert space.

We need the following lemma in this work.

Lemma 1

For any x, y, z in a Hilbert space H and a real number λ in $[0,1]$,

$$\|\lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y - z\|^2 = \lambda \|x - z\|^2 + (1 - \lambda) \|y - z\|^2 - \lambda(1 - \lambda) \|x - y\|^2 \quad (4)$$

Lemma 2

Let $\{\mu_n\}, \{\ell_n\}$ be a nonnegative sequences such that $\sum \ell_n < \infty$ and

$$\mu_{n+1} \leq (1 + \ell_n)\mu_n. \quad \text{Then } \lim \mu_n \text{ exists. If there exists } \{\mu_{n_j}\} \text{ subset } \{\mu_n\} \text{ such that } |\mu_{n_j}| \rightarrow 0$$

as $j \rightarrow \infty$ then $\mu_n \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Main result

Proposition 1

Let E be a normed linear space and let $T: E \rightarrow E$ be asymptotically k -pseudocontractive. Then T is uniformly L -Lipschitzian.

Proof

$$\begin{aligned} \|T^n x - T^n y\|^2 &\leq a_n \|x - y\|^2 + k \|(I-T^n)x - (I-T^n)y\|^2 \\ &\leq \sqrt{a_n} \|x - y\| + \sqrt{k} \|(I-T^n)x - (I-T^n)y\| \end{aligned}$$

so that

$$[(1 - k) \|T^n x - T^n y\| \leq (\sqrt{a_n} + \sqrt{k}) \|x - y\|]$$

Hence,

$$\| |T^{nx} - T^{ny}| \| \leq (\sqrt{a_n} + \sqrt{k}) / (1 - \sqrt{k}) \| |x - y| \|$$

But $a_n \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ so that $\{a_n\}$ is bounded. Hence there exists $a^* > 1$ such that $a_n \leq a^*$ for all $n \geq 0$

Then,

$$\| |T^{nx} - T^{ny}| \| \leq L \| |x - y| \| \text{ for all } x, y \text{ in } D(T)$$

$$\text{Where } L = (\sqrt{a_n} + \sqrt{k}) / (1 - \sqrt{k})$$

Let E be a normed linear space and let $\{T_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a finite family of asymptotically k -pseudocontractive maps. Let α in $(0,1)$, $0 < \alpha < 1$, be a constant and define the auxiliary map

$$T_{n\alpha} = (1 - \alpha)I + \alpha T^n$$

Starting with an arbitrary $x_0 \in E$, define the iterative sequence $\{x_n\}$ by

$$x_{n+1} = T_{m\alpha} x_n; n \geq 0, n+1 \equiv i \pmod N; m = 1 + t\{n\}/\{N\} \quad (11)$$

$$\| |x_{n+1} - x^* | \|^2 = \| |T^{m(n)\alpha} x_n - x^* | \|^2 = \| |(1 - \alpha)x_n + \alpha T^{m(n)} x_n - x^* | \|^2 = (1 - \alpha) \| |x_n - x^* | \|^2 + \alpha \| |T^{m(n)} x_n - x^* | \|^2 - \alpha (1 - \alpha) \| |T^{m(n)} x_n - x_n | \|^2 \leq (1 - \alpha) \| |x_n - x^* | \|^2 + \alpha a_{mi} \| |x_n - x^* | \|^2 + \alpha k_{i(n)} \| |x_n - T^{m(n)} x_n | \|^2 - \alpha (1 - \alpha) \| |T^{m(n)} x_n - x_n | \|^2 = [1 + \alpha (a_{mi} - 1)] \| |x_n - x^* | \|^2 - \alpha (1 - \alpha k_i) \| |x_n - T^{m(n)} x_n | \|^2$$

Now, choose α in $(0,1)$ such that $(1 - \alpha k_i) = c$

For c in $(0,1)$, choose

$$\alpha = 1 - c - k \text{ where } k = \max\{k_{i:n} \mid i \in \{1, \dots, N\}\}$$

we have,

Where $[.]$ denotes the greatest integer function.

Theorem

Let K a nonempty closed convex subset of a real Hilbert Space H

and let $\{T_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a finite family of asymptotically k_i -pseudocontractive maps from K into itself with sequence $\{a_{ni}\}$ subset $[1, +\infty)$ such that

(1). $F = \bigcap_{i=1}^N F(T_i)$ is not empty

(2). $\sum (a_{ni} - 1) < \infty$ for all i .

Starting with an arbitrary x_0 in K , define the iterative sequence $\{x_n\}$ by

equation (11) for some constant $0 < \alpha < 1$. Then

(1). $\{x_n\}$ is bounded

(2). $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \| |x_n - x^* | \|$ exists for $x^* \in F$

(3). $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \| |x_n - T_{ix_n} | \| = 0$; for all i in $\{1, 2, \dots, N\}$.

Proof

Let $x^* \in F$. Now,

$$\| |x_{n+1} - x^* | \|^2 \leq [1 + \alpha (a_{mi} - 1)] \| |x_n - x^* | \|^2 - \alpha c \| |x_n - T^{m(n)} x_n | \|^2 \leq [1 + \alpha (a_{mi} - 1)] \| |x_n - x^* | \|^2$$

Since

$\sum (a_{\{m_i\}} - 1) < \infty$ for all i , it follows by lemma 2 that $\lim_{\{n \rightarrow \infty\}} ||x_n - x^*||$ exists and thus $\{x_n\}$ is bounded.

Let $||x_n - x^*||^2 \leq M$ for all $n > 0$.

Now, for all $n > 0$,

$$c \alpha ||x_n - T^{\{m(n)\}}_{\{i(n)\}} x_n ||^2 \leq [1 + \alpha (a_{\{m_i\}} - 1)] ||x_n - x^* ||^2 - ||x_{\{n+1\}} - x^* ||^2 \leq ||x_n - x^* ||^2 - ||x_{\{n+1\}} - x^* ||^2 + M \alpha (a_{\{m_i\}} - 1).$$

Thus,

$$c \alpha \sum_{\{n \geq 0\}} ||x_n - T^{\{m(n)\}}_{\{i(n)\}} x_n ||^2 \leq ||x_{\{n^*\}} - x^* ||^2 + M \alpha \sum (a_{\{m_i\}} - 1) < \infty.$$

Hence,

$$\lim_{\{n \rightarrow \infty\}} ||x_n - T^{\{m(n)\}}_{\{i(n)\}} x_n || = 0 \quad \{\text{equ 4assreg}\}$$

Now,

$$||x_{\{n+1\}} - x_n || = \alpha ||(1 - \alpha)x_n + \alpha T^{\{m(n)\}}_{\{i(n)\}} x_n - x_n || = \alpha ||x_n - T^{\{m(n)\}}_{\{i(n)\}} x_n ||$$

$$||x_n - T_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || \leq ||x_n - T^{\{m(n+1)\}}_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || + ||T^{\{m(n+1)\}}_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} - T_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || \leq ||x_n - T^{\{m(n+1)\}}_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || + L ||T^{\{m(n+1)-1\}}_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} - x_{\{n+1\}} || \leq ||x_n - T^{\{m(n+1)\}}_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || + L [||T^{\{m(n+1)-1\}}_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} - T^{\{m(n+1)-1\}}_{\{i(n+1-N)\}} x_{\{n+1-N\}} || + ||T^{\{m(n+1)-1\}}_{\{i(n+1-N)\}} x_{\{n+1-N\}} - x_{\{n+1-N\}} || + ||x_{\{n+1-N\}} - x_{\{n+1\}} ||] = ||x_n - T^{\{m(n+1)\}}_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || + L [||T^{\{m(n+1)-1\}}_{\{i(n+1-N)\}} x_{\{n+1-N\}} - T^{\{m(n+1)-1\}}_{\{i(n+1-N)\}} x_{\{n+1-N\}} || + ||T^{\{m(n+1-N)\}}_{\{i(n+1-N)\}} x_{\{n+1-N\}} - x_{\{n+1-N\}} || + ||x_{\{n+1-N\}} - x_{\{n+1\}} ||] \leq ||x_n - x_{\{n+1\}} || + ||T^{\{m(n+1)\}}_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} - x_{\{n+1\}} || + L [L ||x_{\{n+1\}} - x_{\{n+1-N\}} || + ||T^{\{m(n+1-N)\}}_{\{i(n+1-N)\}} x_{\{n+1-N\}} - x_{\{n+1-N\}} || + ||x_{\{n+1-N\}} - x_{\{n+1\}} ||]$$

so that, by using equations ($\{4\text{assreg}\}$) and ($\{\text{assreg}\}$), we have

$$\lim_{\{n \rightarrow \infty\}} ||x_n - T_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || = 0 \quad (14)$$

Furthermore,

$$||x_{\{n+1\}} - T_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || \leq ||x_{\{n+1\}} - x_n || + ||x_n - T_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} ||,$$

so that by equation ($\{4\text{assreg}\}$), we have that

$$\lim_{\{n \rightarrow \infty\}} ||x_{\{n+1\}} - x_n || = 0.$$

Observe that since for all z in $\{Z\}$ (set of integers, $i(z) \equiv z \pmod N$ and $m(z) = 1 + \{z\}/\{N\}$),

but $[\{z\}/\{N\}] = \{z - i(z)\}/\{N\}$ so that $z = (m(z)-1)N - i(z)$. Furthermore, for all n in $\{N\}$, $n+1$ in $\{Z\}$, so that

$$n+1 = (m(n+1)-1)N - i(n+1) \quad \text{equ}\{n+1\}$$

also, for n in $\{N\}$, $n+1-N$ in $\{Z\}$, so for $z = n+1-N$, we have,

$$n+1-N = (m(n+1-N)-1)N - i(n+1-N) \quad \text{equ}\{n-N\}$$

Moreso, subtracting $\{N\}$ from both sides of equation($\{n+1\}$) gives

$$n+1-N = (m(n+1)-1)N - i(n+1) \quad \text{equ}\{N\}$$

Thus comparing equation($\{n-N\}$) and equation($\{N\}$) we have that

$$m(n+1-N) = m(n+1)-1 \text{ and } i(n+1-N) = i(n+1) \quad \text{equ}\{\text{unique}\}$$

So that

so that using equations ($\{\text{assreg}\}$) and (14), we have

$$\lim_{\{n \rightarrow \infty\}} ||x_{\{n+1\}} - T_{\{i(n+1)\}} x_{\{n+1\}} || = 0.$$

Now, let $\{k$ in $I\}$ be arbitrarily chosen, then,

$$\|x_n - T_{i(n+k)}x_n\| \leq \|x_n - x_{n+k}\| + \|x_{n+k} - T_{i(n+k)}x_{n+k}\| + \|T_{i(n+k)}x_{n+k} - T_{i(n+k)}x_n\| \leq (1+L)\|x_n - x_{n+k}\| + \|x_{n+k} - T_{i(n+k)}x_{n+k}\| \leq (1+L)\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \|x_{n+j} - x_{n+j+1}\| + \|x_{n+k} - T_{i(n+k)}x_{n+k}\| \quad \text{equ}\{14a\}$$

Thus

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - T_{i(n+k)}x_n\| = 0 \text{ for all } k \text{ in } \{1, \dots, N\}$$

Hence

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - T_{ix_n}\| = 0 \text{ for all } i \text{ in } \{1, \dots, N\}$$

This completes the proof.

Thus $\{x_n\}$ is an approximate fixed point sequence of T_i for all i in $\{1, \dots, N\}$.

Theorem 2

Suppose in Theorem 1 above, $\{x_n\}$ has a convergent subsequence $\{x_{n_j}\}$, then

$$x_n \rightarrow x^* \text{ in } F$$

Proof

Suppose that $\{x_n\}$ has a convergent subsequence $\{x_{n_j}\}$. Let $x_{n_j} \rightarrow p$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$,

Since $x_n - T_{ix_n} \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for all i in $\{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ it implies that

$$x_{n_j} - T_{ix_{n_j}} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } j \rightarrow \infty \text{ for all } i \text{ in } \{1, 2, \dots, N\} \text{ and that}$$

$T_i x_{n_j} \rightarrow T_i p$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$; for all i by continuity of T_i .

So, $\|p - T_i p\| = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{n_j} - T_{ix_{n_j}}\| = 0$, for all i implying that p in F .

Thus,

$$\|x_{n+1} - p\| \leq \|x_n - p\| \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - p\| \text{ exists but}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_{n_j} - p\| = 0, \text{ so } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - p\| = 0.$$

Hence $x_n \rightarrow x^*(= p)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and that completes the proof.

Remark: Conditions under which $\{x_n\}$ has a convergent subsequence include

- (1). T_i is completely continuous for all i in $\{1, \dots, N\}$
- (2). T_i is demicompact for all i in $\{1, \dots, N\}$
- (3). T_i is semicompact for some i in $\{1, \dots, N\}$
- (4). K is compact.
- (5). K is boundedly compact.

Corollary

Suppose in Theorem 1, the finite family is a singleton, starting with an arbitrary x_0 in K define the iterative sequence $\{x_n\}$ by

$$x_{n+1} = T^\alpha x_n; n > 0$$

(Where $T^\alpha = (1 - \alpha)I + \alpha T$ for some positive constant $0 < \alpha < 1$), then,

- (1). $\{x_n\}$ is bounded
- (2). $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x^*\|$ exists for x^* in F
- (3). $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - T^n x_n\| = 0$; for all I in $\{1, 2, \dots, N\}$.
- (4). $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - T_{ix_n}\| = 0$; for all I in $\{1, 2, \dots, N\}$.

Corollary 2

In Theorem 1, let the finite family be uniformly L_i -Lipschitzian asymptotically demicontractive maps. Then the same conclusions are obtained.

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